

Dark Matter and Neutrino Physics

Contribution from Buenos Aires to the Latin American Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructure

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This document is sent on behalf of the academic faculty members of the Experimental Particle Physics Group at Universidad de Buenos Aires. We begin by summarising our view of the most significant physics questions driving our field and go on to argue how they are addressed through current and future facilities in our Department, in Argentina, and in the world. We then detail our future plans in the fields of direct dark matter searches, and low energy neutrino interactions and oscillations.

Scientific Context

The goal of Particle Physics is to understand the elementary composition and the basic laws of nature. Its most recent experimental discovery, the Higgs boson in 2012, appears to represent the summit in the successful experimental verification of the Standard Model (SM) of particle physics. However, although essentially all of the data from particle accelerators are so far in perfect agreement with the model's predictions, a number of important theoretical and observational considerations point to the necessity of physics beyond the SM (BSM), which is sought for in earnest in the experiments measuring particle production in high energy proton-proton collisions at the Large Hadron Collider. But not all open questions in Particle Physics rely on the high energy frontier, important examples being dark matter, neutrino physics and CP violation.

One of the questions for fundamental science which clearly points to the existence of BSM physics is Dark Matter (DM). Its presence, implied in a growing variety of astrophysical observations, imposes enormous challenges. Unanswered questions include the nature of DM and whether it has non-gravitational interactions, like couplings with SM particles or self-couplings. Beyond collider production and indirect outer space searches for self-annihilation or decay, the major experimental effort has been focused in direct detection which aims at observing low-energy recoils of nuclei induced mainly by collisions with weakly interacting massive particles (WIMPs). However, as the WIMP paradigm becomes experimentally disfavoured, there is nowadays no single compelling theoretical framework for DM, opening up a significantly wider potential parameter space to explore.

Another open question in Particle Physics is the deep mystery of the dominance of matter over antimatter in the universe, especially since CP violation in the quark sector explains only a small fraction of it. Neutrinos may shed light on this problem. They have become more and more accessible to experiment in recent years, through accelerator long-baseline oscillation experiments and the use of reactors for both short baseline and neutrinoless double beta decay experiments. A major effort in the field is and will continue to be devoted to understand their mass hierarchy and to constrain the PMNS matrix.

Objectives

The objective of our group is to install a laboratory to investigate particle detectors with ultra-low threshold based on Skipper-CCD technology, and to apply them to dark matter searches and neutrino physics experiments.

This line of research is being pioneered at the Fermi National Accelerator Laboratory (Fermilab) in the U.S. by a team led by a former student of our group, on whose collaboration this project hinges upon. Skipper-CCDs are silicon pixelated detectors with a spatial resolution of $15\ \mu\text{m}$ and the ability to measure the deposited charge per pixel with a readout noise RMS of $0.1\ e$. This noise level permits to count individual electrons, which translates to the lowest possible threshold detection energy.

This technology is the basis of the SENSEI series of experiments, that are to search for direct observation of dark matter in the low mass domain, from the MeV range up to tens of GeV. This mass region can be accessed using sensors capable of detecting the ionization generated by the nuclear or electronic recoil produced by the elastic scattering of dark matter particles. Thanks to its low readout noise level, Skipper-CCD technology is particularly competitive to test theories that predict light DM in the sub-GeV range. Special care is needed to shield the detector from ambient radiation, be it unstable isotopes or cosmic showers, requiring the installation of the experiment in underground caverns. In this sense, the 1700 m underground ANDES laboratory, proposed to be constructed in parallel with the Agua Negra tunnel in the San Juan province, is a perfect location for late generations of Skipper-CCD based dark matter experiments.

The particle detection technology employed in SENSEI is also directly applicable to the study of neutrino physics exploiting coherent neutrino-nucleus interactions. This channel, predicted in the Standard Model and recently observed by the COHERENT Collaboration, is specially interesting because it embodies an interaction cross-section which is more than two orders of magnitude higher than in the neutrino-nucleon case, because of superposition effects between the nucleus wavefunction and the incident neutrino. The Skipper-CCD detectors are particularly sensitive to the low energy threshold of this interaction, and can be used to measure the high intensity low energy neutrinos escaping from a nuclear reactor. By placing these detectors at different distances close to the reactor core one can explore this interaction channel in search of signs of NP, and to eventually measure the short-baseline oscillations in the propagation of low energy neutrinos.

Finally, Skipper-CCDs also have the potential to exploit the quantum nature of light to capture images of objects with exceptional resolution. Thanks to the technology's heightened sensitivity, the skipper CCD could image objects one photon at a time, increasing the clarity of the signal in quantum imaging experiments. The proposal in the realm of this project is to explore the quantum entanglement of photons as a tool to look for dark photons. The dark photon is a hypothetical spin-1 gauge boson that couples strongly to dark matter Dirac fermions, but couples only weakly to charged SM particles. Several theoretical models accommodate this idea, the simplest one corresponding to a broken U(1) gauge symmetry with kinetic mixing between the corresponding dark photon field and the SM hypercharge field.

Methodology, Construction & operating costs

The installation of an ultra low threshold detectors laboratory, L-DUBU (Laboratorio de Ultra Bajo Umbral), in UBA is expected to start in the second semester of 2020. By the end of 2020 we expect to have a first working setup, including:

- A 50 m² laboratory in the Physics Department at UBA
- Two turbomolecular vacuum stations (10.000 USD)
- Two 10 kW cryorefrigerators reaching temperatures of 4 K (100.000 USD)
- Two high-purity low-radioactivity vacuum chambers (5.000 USD)
- Two ultra low noise readout electronics for CCDs (6.000 USD)
- Support from members of the leading Skipper CCD group in Fermilab

List of the interested scientists in the community

This section summarizes the scientists directly involved in the project and the interested members of the community, categorized by home institution.

- Universidad de Buenos Aires: Gustavo Otero y Garzon, Ricardo Piegaia, Darío Rodrigues, Mariano Cababie.
- Instituto de Investigaciones en Ingeniería Eléctrica, UNS: Guillermo Fernandez Moroni, Leandro Stefanazzi
- Instituto Balseiro: Jeronimo Blostein, Ivan Sidelnik, Xavier Bertou. Miguel Sofo Haro, Mariano Beriso.
- Fermilab: Juan Estrada, Javier Tiffenberg